

STRATEGIC GOALS AND TASKS OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT

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Abstract. *In this article, further improvement of legislation and normative legal framework in the field of tourism activities aimed at forming a holistic concept of tourism development, comprehensive rapid development of all regions and interrelated sectors, and creation of favorable conditions for the activities of tourism industry entities was considered.*

Keywords: *tourism, strategy, industry, complex, area, sector, resource, infrastructure, service.*

INTRODUCTION. The development of tourism in Uzbekistan is aimed at recognizing the trends of increasing attention to tourism in the whole world and making effective use of it.

Today, every country is trying to take advantage of the flow of tourists and increase the position of tourism in the country's economy. Uzbekistan will introduce its rich historical, natural, cultural and ecological resources to the world

their effective use is the demand of the times.

Despite the huge opportunities in the field of tourism, the tourism infrastructure, the quality and level of tourism services, as well as the network management system of Uzbekistan do not meet modern requirements in the conditions of globalization and intense competition. The contribution of tourism to the country's economy, the development of the service sector and the employment of the population lag behind the world average.

In this regard, on January 5, 2019, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Sh. Mirziyev signed Decree No. PF-4095 on measures to ensure the rapid development of the tourism sector of the Republic of Uzbekistan, in which tourism was recognized as a strategic branch of the country's economy.

Research methodology. Systematic approach, abstract-logical thinking, grouping, comparison, factor analysis, selective observation methods were used in the research process.

Analysis and results. In this decree, medium-term perspectives of tourism and hospitality industry are defined and a number of strategic goals are defined.

These strategic goals can be divided into five areas:

creation of favorable economic and organizational-legal conditions for rapid development of tourism;

more complete and effective use of the huge tourism potential of the regions; radical improvement of tourism network management;

creation of national tourism products and their promotion in world markets

to do;

forming a positive image of Uzbekistan in the field of tourism.

A thorough study of the presidential decree and the implementation of its tasks requires a study and analysis of the field of tourism from the perspective of strategic marketing.

In particular, if we consider the state's policy in the field of tourism, they include the following:

a) formation and consistent implementation of a comprehensive concept of tourism development, giving tourism the status of a strategic sector of the economy, diversifying the economy, which should become the leading force for the comprehensive rapid development of all regions and related industries. This direction will introduce strategic thinking in tourism and motivate all leaders to develop a strategy.

b) to further improve the legislation and regulatory framework in the field of tourism activities aimed at creating favorable conditions for the activities of tourism industry entities, to eliminate all obstacles and pitfalls in the development of tourism, visa and registration procedures, state management of the tourism industry and market optimization of the regulation mechanism in a unique way, promotion of entrepreneurial activity in the field of tourism and implementation of measures to develop competition in the market of tourism services. If we analyze this direction, we can see that it includes the development of regulatory and legal mechanisms, which is the main element of the strategic development of the hospitality business. Without simplifying the visa system, there is no need to look at the next points. At the same time, an independent tourist cannot get a visa without a travel agency. In the aforementioned UNWTO survey, visitors rated the complexity of obtaining a visa and general bureaucracy as one of their main negative impressions.

d) rapid development of tourism in the country, more complete and effective use of the existing huge tourism potential, together with traditional cultural and historical tourism, other potential types of tourism - pilgrimage, ecological, educational, ethnographic, gastronomic, sports, treatment-health, rural, industrial, strengthening the social importance of tourism due to the rapid development of business tourism and other types, the development of children, teenagers and youth tourism, family tourism, social tourism for the elderly.

e) to expand international cooperation in the field of tourism activities, first of all, cooperation with the UN World Tourism Organization (UNWTO), influential international and national tourism organizations of foreign countries - active participants of the regional and world markets of tourism services.

Rapid development of tourism industry facilities in all regions of the republic that meet modern world standards, the needs and requirements of tourists - hotels and similar means of accommodation, public catering facilities, transport-logistics structures, information centers, cultural and sports institutions, road transport along the main tourism routes and intensive construction of engineering-communication infrastructure, road infrastructure. The strategic goal of this direction is to provide the tourism sector with a modern material and technical base.

j) Taking into account the trends of international tourism development and the use of modern marketing tools, developing competitive tourism products and services, developing a strategy for their promotion in the domestic and international tourism markets, organizing and developing a favorable tourism information environment.

h) fundamental improvement of the system of quality training of qualified personnel for the tourism industry, especially in the field of management and marketing, training of guides (excursion leaders), regular retraining and upgrading of the employees of tourism activities.

According to the decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the dissolution of the "Uzbekturizm" company and the establishment of the State Committee for the Development of Tourism in Uzbekistan was related to the establishment of the competent body responsible for the implementation of the above strategic tasks. In this regard, a special decision of the President was adopted and the main powers and tasks of the Committee were defined in it.

The State Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan is entrusted with the task of ensuring the formation and implementation of a comprehensive concept of tourism development aimed at the implementation of a unified state policy in the field of tourism.

to carry out marketing research in foreign and domestic markets of tourism services, wide promotion of historical and cultural heritage, preservation and development of the tourism image of the Republic of Uzbekistan, penetration of national tourism products and brands into international tourism markets;

coordinating the development of national and regional programs for the integrated development of internal, inbound and outbound tourism and monitoring their implementation;

coordinating the development of tourism activities, ensuring the establishment of new tourism destinations in the regions;

coordination of the development of quality and safety standards of tourism services, licensing and certification of services in the tourism sector;

optimizing the regulation of the tourism industry by the state and on the basis of market relations and developing competition in the market of tourism services;

expansion of international cooperation with foreign companies operating in the field of tourism, introduction of international and interstate standards and norms to tourism activity and practice.

In order to ensure the full implementation of these tasks, the decisions of the State Committee for Tourism Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan within its powers shall be considered mandatory by state and economic management bodies, state and local management bodies, and by economic entities, regardless of ownership forms and departmental subordination.

Uzbekistan ranks among the top ten countries in the world in terms of the scale of tourism and the number of historical sites. Currently, there are more than seven thousand historical and cultural monuments in our country. Such a rich cultural heritage is abundant, especially in Samarkand. For this reason, in 2001, the city of Samarkand and many cultural objects in its territory were included in the UNESCO World Cultural Heritage List. Samarkand was recognized as one of the 50 cities of the world that a person must visit in his lifetime.

Another important aspect of the presidential decree is the abolition of the visa regime for visiting Uzbekistan for tourists from many countries. This increases the flow of tourists to our country and is more convenient for tourism companies creates an opportunity. When foreign tourists come to our country, it is planned to create comfortable conditions for them at the airports. From April 1, 2017, at the international airports of the cities of Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara and Urgench, necessary measures will be taken to introduce a "green corridor" customs control system for foreign tourists, to pass passport and customs control, a simplified procedure for baggage collection, and to improve the provision of transport services. Events are set to view. It is also a big news that residents, that is, local residents and non-residents - foreign tourists, will pass separate passport control at airports and train stations.

The establishment and development of a convenient tourism information space at the airport and railway stations, including tourism information points, is shown. Now, a tourist arriving in the city can get acquainted with tour operators, hotels and the information they need in this area directly at the airport or train station. Such facilities and opportunities serve to ensure the rapid development of tourism as a strategic branch of the country's economy, and to further enhance the positive image of Uzbekistan as an attractive tourism center.

In Uzbekistan, tourism will be transformed into a strategic sector of the economy, and unprecedented measures will be taken to radically reform this industry, which will determine the qualitative transition of state policy in the field of tourism to a new stage.

From the content of these decrees and decisions, it can be concluded that a strategic approach to the development of tourism has been formed in the Republic of Uzbekistan.

REFERENCES

1. On measures related to the rapid development of the tourism network" Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated January 5, 2019 No. PQ-4095.
2. Decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4755 dated June 19, 2020 "On additional measures to develop the tourism sector in strict compliance with the requirements of the enhanced sanitary and epidemiological safety regime".
3. Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-5249 dated September 22, 2021 "On financial support for activities to be implemented in order to further accelerate large-scale construction and beautification works in Samarkand region and increase tourism potential."
4. Alexandrova A.Yu. International tourism. - M.: Aspect press, 2016. - 470 p.
5. Alimov R., Kamilova M., Kurbanova D. Cluster concept of economic development: theory and practice. - T.: Institut ekonomiki AN Ruz., 2005. - P. 36.
6. Alieva MT, Umurzhanov A. Economy of tourist countries. - T.: Economy - Finance, 2005. - 339 p.
7. Babkin AV Special tourism. - Rostov-on-Don: Phoenix, 2008. - 252 p.
8. Balabanov IT, Balabanov AI Economic tourism. Uchebnoe posobie. - M.: Finance and statistics, 2003. - 176 p.
9. Balabanov IT Economic tourism / IT Balabanov, AI Balabanov - M.: Finance and statistics, 2002. - S. 25.
10. Birzhakov MB Introduction to tourism. – Izdanie 9-e pererabotannoe i dopolnennoe. - SPb.: Izdatelsky dom Gerda, 2007. - 576 p.
11. MS Azimovna Improving The Study Of Consumer Behavior *Gospodarka i Innowacje.*, 109-112 MS Azimovna Stages of the Econometric Research and Modeling Process *Central Asian Journal of Innovations on Tourism Management and Finance* 3
12. MS Azimovna Scientific-Methodical Issues of Evaluation of Marketing Service in Hotels *Central Asian Journal of Innovations on Tourism Management and Finance* 3
13. MS Azimovna Efficiency of advertising activities of trading organizations and ways to increase IT *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities* 12 (3), 93-97
14. Azimovna MS, Ilkhomovna UD Problems of Marketing in the System of Higher Education // *Academic Journal of Digital Economics and Stability.* - 2022. - T. 13. - P. 71-75.
15. Azimovna MS, Ilkhomovna UD, Shokhrukhovich UF INNOVATIVE STRATEGIES OF TOURISM DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN // *EUROPEAN JOURNAL OF INNOVATION IN NONFORMAL EDUCATION.* - 2022. - T. 2. - no. 1. – S. 1-4.